

Perception Of Student Teachers on Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary Level

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ABSTRACT:

Indian system of teacher education has been revamped after implementation of National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE) Regulation, 2014. The pre-service teacher education programme has been designed to develop professional competencies of student teachers. Therefore, NCTE regulation prescribed various forms of integrated approaches in teacher preparation at elementary level and secondary level. Much before NCTE's implementation of Integrated Teacher Education Programme (ITEP), Regional Institutes of Education (RIEs) had planned and successfully implemented the ITEP in Science, Social Science from last four decades. Since a decade, RIE Mysuru has also implemented ITEP ['Master of Science Education' (i.e. M.Sc.Ed.)] for teacher preparation at Senior Secondary, level which is one of its kind in the country. Therefore, the present study has been taken up to explore the perceptions of student teachers on Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level at RIE Mysuru. The study reveals positive opinion of student teachers towards the Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level. It also involved in preparation of large number of competent

teachers for senior secondary level in meeting the needs of the present-day schools.

KEYWORDS:

Integrated Teacher Education Programme, Teacher Education, Senior Secondary level.

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INTRODUCTION

The National Curriculum Framework of Teacher Education developed by NCTE, 2009(NCFTE-2009), emphasized on provision of suitable curricular practices to the student.

NCTE has highlighted the process dimension of areas of curriculum to develop professionalism among student teachers of different stages of school system. It insisted on longer duration of each programme and a holistic perspective of teacher education programme.

Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Primary and Secondary level

National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE), a statutory body under Ministry of Education (MoE) then MHRD, released the notification for initiating Integrated Teacher Education Programme (ITEP) in 2014 in the Country but it has been implemented in reality in 2017.

In order to pursue ITEP programme, a candidates should pass Class 12 with 50% marks (concessions are given for other categories like SC, ST etc.). The ITEP programme is a four-year programme. It includes eight semesters, inclusive of field-based experiences, teaching practice and internship. In a few cases, the maximum time to complete the programme may be extended up to six years.

The NCTE has prepared the guidelines for implementation of

Integrated B.El. Ed. programme, BA.B.Ed/B.Sc.B.Ed. programmes. It gives due emphasis on minimum credits to be earned for specific stage and for specific teacher education programme. Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level

The Regional Institutes of Education (RIE) provides quality pre-service and in-service teacher education programmes in their respective regions and attempts to strive for academic excellence. Much before NCTEs implementation of ITEP, RIEs had planned and successfully implemented the ITEP in Science, Social Science from last four decades.

RIE Mysuru has initiated the Integrated Teacher Education Programme (ITEP) [‘Master of Science Education’ (i.e. M.Sc.Ed.)] in the year 2008 for teacher preparation at Senior Secondary level. For this new programme, there is an intake of 45 students (15 each for Physics, Chemistry and Mathematics respectively). The admission to this course is based on merit. Common Entrance Exam shall be conducted at All India level for the selection process. The scores of senior secondary or the plus two level or the equivalent examination will also be taken into consideration.

The programme is of six academic years comprising twelve semesters, inclusive of field-based experiences, teaching practice and internship. The first four years of this programme is equivalent to Integrated B.Sc. Ed programme and it has got two levels of internship one is at the under graduate level and another at the post graduate level. The programme offers a curriculum that has a fine balance of theory and practice. The course content related to educational components in M.Sc.Ed. (Physics/Chemistry/Mathematics) are equivalent to that of B.Ed. and M.Sc. of University of Mysore and in addition, contains Professional Education components required for teaching of Physics/Chemistry/Mathematics at Senior

Secondary level.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- What are the perceptions of student teachers regarding Institutional support in Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level?
- What are the perceptions of student teachers regarding curriculum and academic activities in Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level?
- What are the perceptions of student teachers regarding career opportunities of Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level?

OBJECTIVES

- To study the perceptions of student teachers regarding Institutional support in Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level.
- To study the perceptions of student teachers regarding curriculum and academic activities in Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level.
- To study the perceptions of student teachers regarding career opportunities of Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level.

METHODOLOGY

The present study employed descriptive study design which explores the perceptions of student teachers on Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level. This programme is of six years where the first four years are equivalent to Integrated B.Sc. Ed programme and it has got two levels of internship. This study has got 239 student teachers (from 1st year M.Sc.Ed. to 6th

year M.Sc.Ed.) as its population. But the present study included an intact group of 71 student teachers who has undergone first level of internship as the sample of the study.

Purposive sampling technique has been used to choose both 5th year and 6th year student teachers of Integrated M.Sc.Ed. Programme from RIE Mysuru. Questionnaire for the target group has been prepared by the investigators to study the perceptions of student teachers on Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level. The questionnaire consists of 22 items, which intended to know about Institutional support, Curriculum & Academic Activities and Career Opportunities of Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level from the target groups.

DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION:

The data was analysed using percentage analysis. It was found in the present study that the percentage of each item of perceptions of student teachers on Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level varied across the given dimensions. Hence, the perceptions of student teachers on ITEP at Senior Secondary level are categorised into three major dimensions. Namely,

- a) Institutional Support;
- b) Curriculum & Academic Activities and
- c) Career opportunities of ITEP.

The questionnaire consists of 22 items which are intended to know about perception of student teachers regarding Institutional Support; Curriculum & Academic Activities and Career opportunities of ITEP.

Research Question 1

What are the perceptions of student teachers regarding Institutional support in Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level?

Table 1. Descriptive analysis of perceptions of student teachers regarding Institutional support in Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level.

Dimensions	Description of Items	Percentage
Institutional Support	1-Have placement cell in the institute	93
	2-Duration of ITEP at Senior Secondary level need not be reduced	73
	3-Orientation to ITEP at Senior Secondary level at the beginning of the course.	59
	4-Innovative criteria for admitting the student-teachers for ITEP at Senior Secondary level.	56
	5-Getting adequate supporting facilities from the institute to become a competent teacher at Senior Secondary level	46
	6-Having required number of qualified and competent teachers to handle all the subjects in the respective departments	38

	7-Having well equipped lab facilities in specific subject discipline	34
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Fig.1.Perception of student teachers regarding Institutional support in ITEP at senior secondary level

Under the Institutional support dimension, 93% of the student teachers gave positive opinion on campus placement cell and 73% of the student teachers appreciated 6 years duration of ITEP at Senior Secondary level. 59% of the student teachers stated that they have been given separate orientation to ITEP at Senior Secondary level in the beginning of the course. 56% of the student teachers said that the institute has an innovative criterion for admitting the student teachers for ITEP at Senior Secondary level. However, adequate supporting facilities from the institute qualified and competent teachers and well-equipped lab facilities have scored less than 50%.

Research Question 2

What are the perceptions of student teachers regarding curriculum and academic activities in Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level?

Table 2. Descriptive analysis of perceptions of student teachers regarding curriculum and academic activities in Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level.

Dimensions	Description of Items	Percentage
Curriculum and Academic Activities	1-Separate internship programme as part of ITEP at Senior Secondary level	100
	2-Curriculum incorporate education component along with specific subject discipline	91
	3-Criteria of evaluation of teaching learning process during your internship activity	85
	4-Duration of Internship programmes have to be increased	80
	5-Student teachers of ITEP at Senior Secondary level perform better than other models of ITEP at Secondary or Elementary level	79
	6-Different curriculum compared to other models of ITEP at Secondary or Elementary level	75

	7-Follow any innovative ways of providing feedback during your internship activity	68
	8-New practices in Micro-teaching as part of ITEP at Senior Secondary level	50
	9-Following innovative methods while transacting the contents in the classroom	42
	10-Following specific assessment method in the classroom	40

Fig.2.Perception of student teachers regarding curriculum and academic activities in ITEP at senior secondary level

Out of the 10 items of the Curriculum and academic activities dimension, all the student teachers revealed that ITEP includes in-

ternship activities for student teachers at senior secondary level. 91% of the student teachers opined their curriculum incorporates education component along with specific subject disciplines. 85% of the student teachers said that they practice unique format of evaluation for teaching learning process during their internship activity. 80% of the student teachers opined that the duration of Internship programme has to be increased. 79% of the student teachers felt that they perform better than other levels (Secondary or Elementary) of ITEP and 75% of the student teachers felt that, they have different curriculum compared to other levels (Secondary or Elementary) of ITEP respectively.

Research Question 3

What are the perceptions of student teachers regarding career opportunities of Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level?

Table 3. Descriptive analysis of perceptions of student teachers regarding career opportunities of Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level.

Dimensions	Description of Items	Percentage
Career Opportunities	1-Internship programme experiences enable to become a professional teacher	95
	2-Like to join teaching profession at Senior Secondary level after the completion of ITEP	83
	3-ITEP at Senior Secondary level serves the needs of the present-day schools	70

	4-All will be placed in good institutes after the completion of ITEP	62
	5-Curriculum empower student teachers to clear competitive exams	30

Fig.3.Perception of student teachers regarding career opportunities of ITEP at senior secondary level

Under Career opportunities dimension, 95% of the student teachers said that internship experiences enable them to become a professional teacher. 83% of the student teachers would like to join teaching profession at Senior Secondary level after the completion of ITEP. 70% of the student teachers mentioned that ITEP at Senior Secondary level serves the needs of the present-day schools. 62% of the student teachers said that all the students will have better placement after the completion of ITEP. 30% student teachers stated that the curriculum of ITEP at senior secondary level does not empower them to clear competitive exams.

CONCLUSION

Pioneering this course RIE Mysuru started Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level in the year 2008. Through the years, it has prepared a large number of competent teachers for senior secondary level keeping in mind the needs of the present-day schools. But the drawback of the programme, as revealed by the student teachers are inadequate faculty, inadequate laboratory facilities, lack of innovative teaching learning methods and assessment techniques followed by most of the faculty in the classroom transaction. All these drawbacks could be overcome by recruiting the efficient and competent teachers, then it may serve the purpose of other elements like innovative teaching learning methods and appropriate assessment techniques. The need of lab facilities if addressed adequately to the respective subject disciplines will help in making the course effective. If the categories in which the student teachers had shown less preference is addressed thoroughly, then Integrated Teacher Education Programme at Senior Secondary level becomes more effective in preparing excellent teachers for schools.

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